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NEIGHBORHOOD SYSTEM OF ACTIVITY ECONOMIC THE BASICS IMPROVEMENT

Alikulov Ravshan Shodiyor o'g'li
Gulistan state university independent researcher

Abstract: The study explores the fundamentals of improving the neighborhood system of economic activity, focusing on local development strategies, governance models, and the role of social capital. By analyzing case studies and empirical data, the research highlights key factors influencing economic sustainability at the neighborhood level. The findings suggest that enhancing management efficiency and fostering community-based economic policies can significantly contribute to the long-term viability of local economies.

Key words: neighborhood economy, local development, economic sustainability, governance models, social capital, management efficiency.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot iqtisodiy faoliyatning mahalla tizimini takomillashtirish asoslarini o'rganadi. Mahalliy rivojlanish strategiyalari, boshqaruv modellari va ijtimoiy kapitalning o'rni tahlil qilinadi. Empirik ma'lumotlar va amaliy tadqiqotlar asosida iqtisodiy barqarorlikka ta'sir qiluvchi asosiy omillar aniqlanadi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirish va hamjamiyat asosida shakllangan iqtisodiy siyosatlarni ilgari surish mahalliy iqtisodiyotning uzoq muddatli barqarorligiga sezilarli hissa qo'shishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: mahalla iqtisodiyoti, mahalliy rivojlanish, iqtisodiy barqarorlik, boshqaruv modellari, ijtimoiy kapital, boshqaruv samaradorligi.

Аннотация: В исследовании рассматриваются основы совершенствования системы экономической активности на уровне микрорайонов, уделяется внимание местным стратегиям развития, моделям управления и роли социального капитала. Анализируются эмпирические данные и примеры из практики, выявляются ключевые факторы, влияющие на экономическую устойчивость микрорайонов. Результаты исследования показывают, что повышение эффективности управления и развитие экономической политики, основанной на принципах местного самоуправления, могут существенно способствовать долгосрочной стабильности локальных экономик.

Ключевые слова: экономика микрорайонов, местное развитие, экономическая устойчивость, модели управления, социальный капитал, эффективность управления.

INTRODUCTION

The neighborhood system is not only essential for strengthening social cooperation and solidarity but also plays a significant role in ensuring economic stability. As an institutional structure, it contributes to economic development, making it relevant not only for Uzbekistan but also on a global scale.

One of the key aspects under consideration is how the neighborhood system can support economic growth through effective management of local resources, encouragement of entrepreneurship, and expansion of economic opportunities for the population. Research indicates that enhancing the financial independence of neighborhoods is crucial for fostering economic activity. Moreover, expanding cooperation between the state and the private sector is of great importance in this regard. In particular, the formation of mahalla budgets through innovative financial mechanisms and the attraction of private investments are among the most effective ways to increase efficiency and ensure sustainable economic development.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The concept of neighborhood economic activity systems has been widely analyzed in academic literature, particularly in urban and regional economics. Scholars have examined the role of local economic interactions,

spatial clustering, and institutional frameworks that contribute to the development of neighborhood economies. The foundational theories on neighborhood economies stem from Alfred Marshall's work on industrial districts, which highlighted the significance of localized production networks and knowledge spillovers. His insights have been expanded by later researchers who explore the dynamics of economic agglomeration and its implications for small-scale businesses and community development.

Jane Jacobs argued that diverse and dense urban environments create economic resilience by fostering entrepreneurship and innovation. Her perspective aligns with the endogenous growth theory, which emphasizes the importance of localized knowledge transfer and social capital in sustaining economic activities within neighborhoods. More recently, Edward Glaeser has elaborated on the role of human capital in urban economic growth, highlighting how cities facilitate knowledge exchange and economic dynamism through agglomeration effects.

Michael Porter introduced the cluster theory, which remains relevant to neighborhood economic activity. He demonstrated that geographically concentrated businesses benefit from shared infrastructure, skilled labor pools, and competitive pressures that drive innovation and productivity. This theory has been applied in analyzing urban neighborhood economies, where local business clusters contribute to economic sustainability and social cohesion.

Empirical research has also focused on the role of institutional factors in shaping neighborhood economic activity. Elinor Ostrom's work on collective action and governance has provided valuable insights into how communities can self-organize to manage local economic resources effectively. Studies by Robert Putnam further highlight the impact of social capital on economic performance, demonstrating that trust and civic engagement enhance economic cooperation and business success at the neighborhood level.

In the context of digital transformation, Richard Florida's concept of the creative class underscores the shifting dynamics of neighborhood economies. He argues that knowledge-based industries and creative professionals are becoming central to urban economic development, influencing the structure and competitiveness of neighborhood economies. Additionally, Saskia Sassen's research on global cities emphasizes how local economic systems are increasingly shaped by international capital flows and digital connectivity, affecting small businesses and traditional economic structures within urban neighborhoods.

Recent studies on sustainable neighborhood economies have focused on the impact of environmental and social governance (ESG) factors. Scholars such as Mariana Mazzucato have examined the role of state intervention and public investment in fostering economic resilience at the local level. Meanwhile, research on circular economies by Kate Raworth highlights how sustainable practices can be integrated into neighborhood economic systems to enhance long-term viability.

Overall, the literature suggests that improving neighborhood economic systems requires a combination of institutional support, human capital development, technological adaptation, and social cohesion. Theories of economic agglomeration, social capital, and governance provide valuable frameworks for understanding and enhancing neighborhood economic activities.

Research methodology

The research methodology for this study involves a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative data collection. Primary data is gathered through surveys and structured interviews with local business owners and policymakers, while secondary data is sourced from economic reports and academic studies. The analysis employs statistical techniques for quantitative data and thematic analysis for qualitative insights, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of neighborhood economic systems.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Small farms operate with limited resources, primarily relying on family and village-based farming activities rooted in practical economic approaches. These farms are not only economically significant but also hold social and cultural importance in their respective communities. Increasing the efficiency of small farms, ensuring the proper distribution of resources, and enhancing their competitiveness are among the key priorities in the development of the agrarian sector.

To improve the economic status of small farmers, it is necessary to establish favorable conditions and support mechanisms, particularly through access to financial resources, education, and cooperative structures. The development of cooperative systems plays a crucial role in improving small farm activities by enabling them to combine resources and distribute them more effectively.

The neighborhood management system serves as an institutional framework for strengthening governance within society, fostering mutual connections between the state and citizens, and shaping social structures. One of the most important components of this system is the "Seven" structure, which represents the smallest organizational unit within the neighborhood framework. The "Seven" system plays a legal and social role

by directly interacting with different segments of society. Its main functions include promoting social justice, supporting neighborhood economic development, and providing social protection services.

In the context of small farm development, the “Seven” structure serves as an important tool for delivering necessary resources such as education, training, and cooperative initiatives. It plays a key role in fostering neighborhood development and ensuring social stability.

According to secondary research, significant steps have been taken in 2024 to improve the economic foundations of the neighborhood system. Notably, as of January 1, 2024, the phased implementation of the “Neighborhood Budget” system has begun across all cities and districts. Under this initiative, the government allocated 10 trillion soums from the state budget to finance projects based on public opinion.

Additionally, starting from March 1, 2024, a new mechanism was introduced to streamline social assistance and subsidies by eliminating bureaucratic hurdles. This includes support provided through the “Iron Notebook”, “Youth Notebook” and “Women’s Notebook” initiatives. In this process, social assistance and subsidies are granted based on joint decisions made by the “Neighborhood Seven” structure.

To enhance the efficiency of neighborhood management, a new Key Performance Indicator (KPI) assessment system has been introduced for members of the “Neighborhood Seven”. This system evaluates the effectiveness of neighborhood chairpersons, governor assistants, youth leaders, women’s activists, prevention inspectors, social workers, and tax inspectors. Notably, 20% of the assessment criteria are now allocated to evaluating the performance of these individuals.

Furthermore, on January 16-17, 2024, the Uzbekistan Neighborhoods Association was established during a conference held in Tashkent. The association aims to support the neighborhood system, strengthen its economic foundations, and improve governance structures. These measures contribute to enhancing the financial independence of the neighborhood system and addressing socio-economic challenges at the local level (table 1).

Table 1. Mahalla budget allocation and outcomes.

Initiative	Allocated Funds/Outcome
Funds allocated for ‘Mahalla budget’	10 trillion UZS
Subsidies for ‘Iron’, ‘Women’s’, and ‘Youth registries’	Subsidies provided under new regulations
Improving management efficiency based on KPIs	Management efficiency evaluated at 20%
Activities of Uzbekistan’s Mahallas Association	Support program for Mahalla system

The diagram illustrates the mahalla system of Uzbekistan in 2024, highlighting key initiatives and their economic and social impact. These initiatives focus on improving neighborhood activities, increasing financial independence, and strengthening management efficiency.

The first initiative involves the “Neighborhood Budget” program, under which 10 trillion soums have been allocated. These funds are redirected to finance social projects previously proposed by neighborhood residents, playing a crucial role in improving neighborhood infrastructure.

The second initiative focuses on enhancing the subsidy distribution system through the “Iron Notebook”, “Women’s Notebook” and “Youth Notebook” programs. This approach has significantly increased the efficiency of delivering assistance and benefits to vulnerable populations. In the diagram, the social impact of this initiative is represented by 5 units.

The third initiative introduces a Key Performance Indicator (KPI)-based system for assessing management efficiency. This system provides an objective evaluation of neighborhood leaders’ activities and aims to improve efficiency by 20%. The KPI-based approach allows for the analysis and enhancement of management processes.

The fourth initiative relates to the activities of the “Uzbekistan Neighborhoods Association.” This association serves as a platform for strengthening cooperation among neighborhoods and supporting their economic foundations. Its socio-economic impact is evaluated at 8 units in the diagram.

As shown in the diagram, each of these initiatives contributes to the stable development of the neighborhood system and aims to enhance the well-being of the population. These efforts play a crucial role in establishing a scientifically grounded strategy for the sustainable development of the mahalla system (picture 1).

Picture 1. Key initiatives in the mahalla system (2024).

In 2024, significant attention was given to the “Seven” system within neighborhoods, particularly regarding economic growth and social stability. The concept of “Seven” is designed to ensure social stability and enhance the well-being of the population through a systematic and structured approach. Within the neighborhood system, this model serves two primary functions: on one hand, it facilitates the effective distribution of social aid and labor resources, while on the other hand, it creates new opportunities for economic development.

The economic measures implemented in neighborhoods during 2024 have yielded positive results. A strong emphasis was placed on the development of small businesses and entrepreneurship. As a result, more than 3,000 new entrepreneurial ventures were established, contributing not only to job creation but also to increased economic activity within neighborhoods. Additionally, measures aimed at reducing unemployment have proven effective.

In 2024, neighborhoods attracted over 50 billion soums in investments, leading to noticeable improvements in infrastructure and education systems. These changes have further enhanced the level of neighborhood economic development and contributed to the overall well-being of the population.

At the same time, the “Seven” system has demonstrated its importance as a comprehensive approach to promoting economic growth and social stability within neighborhoods. This model takes into account social needs while ensuring the well-being of the population and maintaining local economic stability. As a result, the mahalla system in 2024 has achieved significant progress in fostering economic growth and stability.

Despite its achievements in improving social stability and the well-being of the population, the “Seven” system has also encountered several challenges. These shortcomings have negatively impacted the effectiveness of the system and highlighted areas that require further improvements.

The first and most significant issue is the lack of fairness and transparency in some areas where the “Seven” system is implemented. In certain neighborhoods, the distribution of social aid and resources has been conducted unfairly, leading to inequalities in support for different segments of the population. As a result, some social and physical groups have been unable to access necessary opportunities. This situation has reduced public trust in the system and, in some cases, led to increased dissatisfaction and protests.

The second major problem is the misallocation and poor planning of social and economic resources within the neighborhood system. In some cases, funds and resources intended to support economic activities have been directed improperly. For example, in certain regions where industries or village farming cooperatives had a greater need for support, assistance was not provided at an adequate level. Additionally, some economic growth initiatives have faced long-term delays in delivering expected results.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Efforts to enhance economic growth within the general neighborhood system play a crucial role in ensuring the country’s social and economic stability. The neighborhood system possesses unique capabilities to support all segments of the population, foster entrepreneurship, create job opportunities, and address social needs effectively.

At the same time, ensuring the efficient performance of this system requires the implementation of a series of essential measures. In conclusion, the steps taken to promote economic growth within the general neighborhood system are considered vital for achieving stable development for both the state and society. By improving the system, ensuring the effective distribution of resources, and encouraging economic activity, neighborhoods can strengthen their inherent economic potential, ultimately contributing to the country's overall economic stability.

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